

A Comparative Economic Analysis of Malaysia and Pakistan

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Comparison of economies of Malaysia and Pakistan

This report demonstrates the comparison between the economies of Pakistan and the newly emerging economy of Malaysia. The comparison is done through analyzing and comparing world development indicators. We have chosen 12 indicators with a time span of 20 years from 2000 to 2020. The changing trends over the chosen time periods is explained for both of the countries. These trends are then compared with each other for the analysis of the economies of the two countries.

Health Expenditure:

Figure 1

Health expenditure includes healthcare services and goods spent during each year to maintain, promote or improve health. Health expenditure of Malaysia indicates an increase from year 2000 to year 2007 but then it decreases. The health expenditure again increases at the year 2009 but then decreased at 2010. The expenditure spent on health showed a gradual increase from year 2011 to the year 2018 and reached its peak to 3.8 and then showed a sharp decrease in the year 2019. On the other hand, health expenditure of Pakistan showed an opposite trend till the year 2018 but showed a sharp decline at the year 2019. The expenditure of health decreased from the year 2000

to 2001, then it again declined in the year 2003 and 2004 due to the important political events. The expenditure showed a sharp increase in the year 2007 but again decreased at 2008 for the reason of great depression that had a huge impact on economy of Pakistan since it has a fragile economy. This expenditure started to rise gradually from the year 2012 to the year 2018 and reached its peak at 3.2 but it dropped again in the year 2019. Health expenditure of Malaysia are higher than that of Pakistan at all years except 2002 and 2007.

Death Crude Rate:

Figure 2

Death rate crude (per 1000 people) refers to the total number of resident deaths living in a specific area. It is general health status indicator of a geographic area. Death crude rate of Malaysia showed a gradual increase from the year 2000 to the year 2019. According to WHO report, the prime reasons for mortality rates were periodic measles outbreaks though rates of immunization is good in Malaysia. For Malaysia, dengue, HIV and TB remained some challenges. Dengue remains a challenge. NCDs was a major cause of death that had posed serious threats to lives of people in Malaysia especially the adult people. Mental health problems are prevailing in both children and adults. One of the reason of increasing mortality is environmental health problems due to water and air pollution and extractive industries activities.

However, death crude rate of Pakistan showed an opposite trend. It indicates a gradual decrease in death rate from the year 2000 to the year 2019. One of the reason can be terrorism attacks due to

9/11 incident in US and Al-Qaeda and Taliban militants' threats to Pakistan. Pakistan reduced terrorism in the country by military operations in Pakistan that were conducted by Army of Pakistan. According to WHO report life expectancy rate increased over time in Pakistan. It had shown an increase of 3 years from the year 2000 to the year 2012. According to WHO the top ten health causes are Lower respiratory infections, Birth asphyxia and birth trauma, Ischemic heart disease, Stroke, Diabetes mellitus, Pre term birth complications, Tuberculosis, Diarrheal diseases, Neonatal sepsis and infections and Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing:

Figure 3

Agriculture, Forestry, and Fishing correspond to crop cultivation and livestock production. It involves reaping and growing organic products for trade and manufacturing.

The agricultural sector accounts for around 8 percent of GDP in Malaysia and has around 10 percent of people working in this sector. In Malaysia agriculture, forestry and fishing had a high share of one-third of GDP but it decreased between 1970 and 2000 to one tenth of GDP. This trend also led to decrease in labor force employed in this sector. Although rice is the main crop, its production dropped despite technological innovations but due to government schemes its production increased after 2000. For Malaysia, the indicator of agriculture, forestry, and fishing shows a trend in a zig-zag manner. It decreases in the year 2001 and shows a gradual increase afterward till the year 2004. In the year 2005, it declines again and then shows an increase in the

year 2007. Malaysia reaches its peak in the year 2011 but then decreases gradually till the year 2016. This indicator rises in the year 2017 but then shows a slight decrease.

Pakistan being an agro-based economy has agriculture, fishing, and forestry indicator higher than that of Malaysia all the years. This indicator accounts for 18 percent of the GDP of Pakistan and almost half of the people living in Pakistan earn their livelihood from Agriculture, Forestry, and Fishing. The factor of livestock contributes to almost half of the agriculture sector. The fishery is also showing rapid growth in Pakistan while 4% of the land of Pakistan is occupied by forests which are major sources of food, medicine, paper, and latex. This indicator shows a decrease in the year 2002 and then remains consistent till the year 2005. In the year, 2006 the indicator declined as Pakistan had to suffer losses due to an earthquake that occurred at the end of the year 2005. It, then, started to rise and reached its peak in the year 2011. This indicator declined in the year 2012 and showed consistent growth in the following years.

GDP Growth:

Figure 4

The economy of Malaysia after Asian Crisis is continuously increasing and its status is likely to elevate as well. It is likely to transition to a high income country from lower middle income country by the year 2024. The prime reason for its increase in GDP growth is openness to trade and increase in investment which has led to increase in income growth and increase in living standards as well. Its GDP growth also rose due to being an agriculture and commodity based economy. The graph

shows a sharp decline in GDP growth in the year 2001 due to Japan weakening and US slowdown in economy as Malaysia was dependent upon foreign investments to a great extent. GDP growth increased and decreased in a zig zag manner during the following years. It again decreased sharply in the year 2009 due to contagious effects of global recession. Malaysia had a focus on international trade and was dependent on a few primary products due to which it suffered a lot due to any crisis in the economy of its trading partners. Its GDP again had a sharp increase in gdp in the year 2010 but was still lower than gdp in the year 2000. Malaya's GDP growth remained in a zig zag manner afterwards.

Pakistan is a developing country with fragile economy. Its economy has suffered a lot due to lack of law reinforcement, political instability and corruption. It has fast growing population but its rate of GDP growth is not enough to deal with such large population. The major sector that accounts for nearly half of the GDP is services sectors that includes defense, public administration and wholesale and retailing. Industry also contributes to around 25 percent of GDP of Pakistan. It relies on industries, agriculture, remittances and manufacturing for GDP growth. GDP of Pakistan is lower than that of Malaysia at all points except the years 2004, 2016 and 2018. GDP of Pakistan dropped in the year 2002 as the expenditures were reduced to meet the IMF fiscal target. GDP reached its peak in the year 2004 that was the highest in two decades. The main reason was due to increased agricultural growth, great growth in services sector and most importantly, immense performance in large scale manufacturing. The increased GDP growth led to increase in consumer demand and increased consumption. The GDP showed a gradual decline in the following years till the year 2008. The GDP growth rate increased in 2009 and then declined again at 2010. The GDP growth rate increased gradually till the year 2018 and then sharply declined. According to an article of The News, the decline in GDP growth in 2019 is due to incompetent economic team driven by IMF. Pakistan GDP decreased due to devaluation of Pakistani rupee and decreased gdp growth rate. The annual liabilities and debt of the government were also fairly high in the year 2019.

Imports:

Figure 5

Imports of goods and services includes the value of all goods and services bought from other countries. They act as a keystone in representing and informing about the foreign trade of a country.

An overall decrease was observed in the imports of Malaysia as a % of GDP. Although they were fluctuating however the final result was a decrease in last 20 years. The imports were highest in 2000, a total of 100% of GDP. During that time period as the country was still recovering from the Asian Financial Crisis of 1997 so the total value of imports in 2000 was \$81,957 million. Malaysia's imports are mainly based on electronic products 29.4%, chemicals 9.5%, petroleum products 9.3% and machinery and appliances 8.7%. After this the imports decreased however a rise was noted once again in 2005 which was due to the high imports of intermediate goods. Since the GDP per capita of Malaysia was growing constantly, the consumption was also growing faster therefore even till 2019 the imports remained at almost 60% of GDP. But the country was able to decrease it from 100% to 60% over the course of 20 years.

On the other hand, since the GDP per capita of Pakistan is lower in comparison hence the overall consumption is low as well. The percentage of imports grew slightly to almost 20% of GDP during these 20 years. Otherwise, the rate was almost constant from 2010-2019. Slight increase was noted

in 2007 and 2009 which can be associated with the financial impact of the global crisis of that time. During recession, the lack of growth in local production eventually leads to the country being more dependent on imports. The imports of Pakistan are also mostly made up by petroleum and petroleum-based products, capital goods, industrial raw materials, and fertilizers.

Exports:

Figure 6

Exports of a country refer to the local goods and services that are sold to other countries, also representing the international trade of a country. An overall decrease was noted in the exports of Malaysia from 120% to almost 60% of GDP. This loss in exports has been labeled as the worst slump in the Malaysian exports in the past years. This loss was attributed to lower exports to some of its main trading partners that included the European Union, Thailand, Singapore, Saudi Arabia, and Japan. In contrast, the exports to China increased by a significant amount. Some of main exports of Malaysia include: electronic products, palm oil, liquefied natural gas, petroleum, rubber, and wood products.

Meanwhile, the exports of Pakistan once again remained almost constant. These exports consist mainly of textile, leather-based goods, carpets, sports goods, and various vegetables and fruits. Its main trading partners are China, US, UK, and Germany. Since the manufacturing sector of Pakistan is weak, it is difficult to increase the number of exports by a significant amount.

Moreover, due to some internal factors such as corruption and monopolies in the local market, there is a great focus in imports only. The government tend to overlook the exports or focus on the growth of this side of the equation.

Trade Openness:

Figure 7

Trade openness of a country refers to the measure of how involved a country is in the global market. This can be measured as ratio of sum of exports and imports to GDP. Increased trade openness indicates a positive growth of the economy as the country is more open to trade with other countries, this not only increases the imports and exports but also helps in productivity by technological growth and development.

At the beginning of the specified time period (2000-2019) the trade openness of Malaysia was relatively high almost 220% of the GDP. After a slight decrease, it raised once again during 2004-2005 however decreased afterwards till 2019 to almost 120%. An overall decrease of 100% of GDP was experienced during this course. This can be due to the high decrease in exports and imports of the country. Since the country is gradually becoming self-sufficient due to development, it has reduced its imports. As for exports, due to some restrictions and barriers as well as some trade partnerships the exports of the country have been cut down greatly.

Due to low consumption the imports and exports as a percentage of GDP of Pakistan have remained almost unchanged through-out, the trade openness of the country has also been constant

for the past 20 years. A slight increase of maybe 5% would have taken place. This factor has posed an obstacle to development of the country as Pakistan cannot be referred to as a trade open country, it does not have access to up to date technological methods or products that boosts the local economy. Hence, this lack of openness justifies the weak manufacturing and low productivity of Pakistan.

Manufacturing:

Figure 8

Manufacturing refers to the process of producing goods through different methodologies depending on the use of labour and other capital goods such as machinery, and tools. This can also involve raw materials purchased locally or imported.

The manufacturing sector has played a key role in the economic development of Malaysia. As per the Department of Statistics Malaysia a significant number of employees 1,028,301 are engaged in the local manufacturing sector, with salary average of RM3,122 paid per employee. The manufacturing as percentage of GDP was recorded at 30% in 2000. Even though it experienced a slight increase in the period of 2004-2005 but it soon experienced a constant decline bringing it down to almost 21% by the end of 2019. As the international demand for the Malaysian products fell, the production also dropped down eventually. Another factor noted was the burden of manufacturers as the prices of inputs and raw materials kept on increasing due to which producers had to cut down on their production to lower costs and the burden.

On the contrary, an increase in the manufacturing as a percentage of GDP was recorded. As the manufacturing sector is the third largest of the country, it has played a crucial part in contributing to the economy of Pakistan. Despite, some limitations and difficulties the sector has displayed immense development and growth. This is due to the constant improving quality of the local goods that has resulted in increased international demand for its products. Some goods that are highly contributing include the textile sector and sports goods industry. After agriculture, the cotton textile industry is also regarded as contributing greatly to the real GDP of the country and accounting for approximately 65% of the country’s exports. By the end of 2019, the industry sector made up almost 18.34% share of the GDP.

Education:

Figure 9

Malaysia views education as a human capital which is basically an investment that will pay off in the future also called as “human capital as determinant of growth”. The trend of education expenditure as a percentage of GDP can be seen in the form of fluctuations. Starting from 2000, the expenditure on education increased from 5.9% to 7.6% in 2002. After that, it is seen to sharply decline from 2003 to 2005. The expenditure is higher in 2006 but gradually decreases till 2008 reaching 3.9%. The expenditure sharply increases in 2009 to 5.9% but is seen to decrease by 1% in 2010. From 2011 to 2019, the expenditure has been gradually decreases to a value of 4.1% in 2019. Initially, the education was mostly funded by government with strict laws and regulations

regarding admissions and recruitment of teachers. There were less private institutions and Malaysian students were going abroad for quality high education causing a loss for Malaysia. The decline in 2005 could also be because of liberalization of agriculture and manufacturing sector, which caused the education sector to be neglected. Malaysia now is aiming to make itself the education hub providing quality education. The education sector was liberalized giving private institutions autonomy to cater better to the need of international standard education. The fluctuations in the trend could also be because of the changing blueprints for education as Malaysia aimed to keep up with the changing advancements and technologies of the world. Currently, Malaysia aims to make its mark in the global economy and to have its institutions ranked in the leading institutions of the world.

As evident by the trend of government expenditure in Pakistan, Pakistan paid very less attention towards its education sector since the start. Starting from 2000, the expenditure on education as percent of GDP has decreased till 2003, followed by an increase from 2004 (1.76%) to 2008 (2.74%). The expenditure declined from 2009 to 2012 reaching 2.13%. The expenditure is seen to rise from 2013, reaching peak at 2016 reaching expenditure of 3%. It decreases slightly to 2.8% in 2017. This overall decrease in expenditure on education in Pakistan as compared to Malaysia can be explained by government's negligence on education sector for the past years. It could also be because of lower demand for education in Pakistan due to sociocultural issue and gender discrimination. Recently, about 70% of Pakistani students go abroad for higher education and the percentage is expected to increase. The current allocation of budget to education is Rs. 83.3 billion which although is a slight increase from the previous fiscal year but is still not enough as compared to international standards. Currently, budget allocation to education equals 2.5% of the total GDP which is lower than the international standard of 4%.

Female top managers:

Figure 10 : Female top managers MYS vs PK

The percentage of firms having female top managers was 8.7% in 2007. This percentage increased to 26.3% in 2015. This percentage is comparatively higher than Pakistan but is still quite low. The increase in the percentage from 2007 to 2015 is because Malaysia focuses on the education of women especially at the tertiary level, as education is the determinant of a female's career. In 2015, the percentage of women getting tertiary education was 58.2%. Although Malaysia has increased the percentage of firms having female top managers but the percentage is low due to problems like gender inequality and the fact that female top managers face a difficult environment to adjust rather than the male top managers. Malaysia has a score of only 0.68 on the gender parity index.

Pakistan reported only 6% firms that had female top managers in 2013. One of the major reasons is gender inequality in Pakistan. Females are not allowed to get education in many areas of Pakistan. Pakistan ranked 151 out of 153 countries on the gender parity index. Although the percentage of female population in Pakistan has increased to 62% in 2020, there are still very less job opportunities for women. This is because of the socio-cultural problems that Pakistan faces. This can also be because, apart from education, women are not given trainings that would teach them to effectively communicate and interact in the work environment. This also results in women not being able to get to top managing positions.

Services:

Figure 11

Service sector has been a key area for Malaysia to improve its economy. Service sectors of Malaysia mainly include business, technology, healthcare, oil and gas, hospitality, transport, logistics and research and development. The output from services sector as percentage of GDP is shown by the graph. The output is seen to increase in the span of the 20 years. From 46.3% in 2000, the expenditure increased to 54.2% in 2019. Services sector is also important for Malaysian economy as it accounts for most of the employment in Malaysia. In 2020, around 60% of the population of Malaysia worked in the service sector. Another cause in this expansion in the service sector would be internationalization of the service sector. International companies were allowed to invest in Malaysia causing the increase in service sector.

The service sector of Pakistan is very diverse. It is divided into four main types namely, distributive services, producer services, personal services and social services. These types are further classified into subsectors including transport, communications, hospitality, entertainment, public administration and defense. The output of service sector has been higher in Pakistan than in Malaysia. Although Pakistan is an agricultural economy, but the trend is seen to be changing. Due to urbanization, people are moving towards service sector for employment. In 2020, employment in Pakistan due to agriculture sector was 35.8% whereas employment due to service sector was 38.3%.

Textile and clothing:

Figure 12

Textiles and clothing are included in the most important export goods of Malaysia. The graph shows a fluctuating trend. In 2000, the output from textiles and clothing was 4% of the total manufacturing output. This output gradually decreased to 1.9% in 2008. A rise was seen in the output in 2009 where it equaled 2.2%. After minor fluctuations, the output reached 2.05% in 2018. The decrease in the output in the early 2000s could be because of the global recession and its impacts. The demand of the goods decreased internationally, which ultimately caused a decrease in the production of these goods. Malaysia is moving towards the expansion of textile and clothing by increasing investment in this sector and by making effective use of technology.

Pakistan reported an output of 33.3% in 2001, which decreased to 28.8% in 2006. The reason could be same as for Malaysia. The global recession had impact on the demand and supply of almost all the economies of the world. The international demand for textiles and clothing decreased which caused a decrease in output from textiles and clothing. Another factor due to the decline can also be the lack of technological advancement in Pakistan. Moreover, lack of government support, inefficient policies and power shortages in the country can also be reasons for this decline.

Conclusion:

Malaysia can be regarded as a developing country which is almost close to becoming a developed country. Its economic development is a prove of how the economy is progressing. This further indicates a strong position as compared to the economy of Pakistan. Looking at some statistics:

- Pakistan's GDP per capita recorded in 2017 was \$5,400 whereas that of Malaysia was \$29,100.
- According to data of 2017, 6% of people in Pakistan are unemployed but only 3.4% are unemployed in Malaysia.
- The taxpayer rate of 2016 in Pakistan was 20% but the same rate was 28% in Malaysia.

These economic factors and differences depict that the Malaysian economy has made far more progress as compared to that of Pakistan. It may be behind in some aspects such as manufacturing and focus on foreign trade but eventually it is superior to Pakistan in economic terms.

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